

Supplementary Information for

Early-life adversity accelerates cellular ageing and affects adult inflammation: Experimental evidence from the European starling

Daniel Nettle*, Clare Andrews, Sophie Reichert, Tom Bedford, Claire Kolenda, Craig Parker, Carmen Martin-Ruiz, Pat Monaghan², Melissa Bateson

* Corresponding author: daniel.nettle@ncl.ac.uk

Model tables

Table S1. Linear mixed model results for daily weight during the experimental manipulation (days 5 – 15). LRT: likelihood ratio test.

Effect	Parameter estimate (s.e.)	LRT	p-value
Age	3.46 (0.16)	816.44	<0.01
Sex (Male)	-0.97 (1.54)	0.35	0.56
Amount (Plenty)	-3.20 (1.80)	52.14	<0.01
Effort (Hard)	2.99 (1.89)	5.82	0.02
Amount*Effort	-2.80 (2.34)	4.45	0.03
Age*Sex	0.01 (0.13)	0.23	0.63
Age*Amount	1.10 (0.16)	125.58	<0.01
Age*Effort	-0.65 (0.16)	8.46	<0.01
Age*Amount*Effort	0.54 (0.20)	7.04	<0.01

Table S2. Linear mixed model results for tarsus length at day 15, tarsus length at day 56, and change in tarsus length between days 15 and 56.

Effect	Parameter estimate (s.e.)	LRT	p-value
<i>Tarsus length at day 15</i>			
Sex (Male)	0.46 (0.30)	2.27	0.13
Amount (Plenty)	1.22 (0.35)	24.79	<0.01
Effort (Hard)	-0.40 (0.37)	0.02	0.89
Amount*Effort	0.80 (0.45)	2.91	0.09
<i>Tarsus length at day 56</i>			
Sex (Male)	0.53 (0.28)	3.47	0.06
Amount (Plenty)	0.85 (0.32)	18.33	<0.01
Effort (Hard)	-0.28 (0.34)	0.21	0.64
Amount*Effort	0.72 (0.42)	2.76	0.10
<i>Tarsus length change between day 15 and day 56</i>			
Sex (Male)	0.09 (0.13)	0.45	0.50
Amount (Plenty)	-0.37 (0.15)	12.08	<0.01
Effort (Hard)	0.14 (0.16)	0.62	0.43
Amount*Effort	-0.08 (0.19)	0.19	0.66

Table S3. Linear mixed model results for age at fledging.

Effect	Parameter estimate (s.e.)	LRT	p-value
Sex (Male)	0.24 (0.28)	0.69	0.41

Amount (Plenty)	-0.25 (0.33)	9.92	<0.01
Effort (Hard)	0.90 (0.34)	0.66	0.42
Amount*Effort	1.19 (0.42)	6.69	<0.01

Table S4. Linear mixed model results for weight at day 56.

Effect	Parameter estimate (s.e.)	LRT	p-value
Tarsus length (day 56)	1.52 (0.68)	3.90	0.05
Sex (Male)	2.10 (1.10)	3.43	0.06
Amount (Plenty)	-2.44 (1.30)	0.18	0.68
Effort (Hard)	-3.70 (1.24)	1.24	0.27
Amount*Effort	4.61 (1.57)	7.52	<0.01

Table S5. Linear mixed model results for standardized telomere length change (D statistic¹, more negative number indicates greater attrition) between time points.

Effect	Parameter estimate (s.e.)	LRT	p-value
<i>Day 5 to day 56 (beginning of experiment to juvenile period)</i>			
Telomere length day 5	-0.29 (0.08)	6.85	<0.01
Sex (Male)	0.10 (0.07)	1.72	0.19
Amount (Plenty)	0.20 (0.07)	7.14	<0.01
Effort (Hard)	-0.16 (0.07)	5.20	0.02
Amount*Effort	-0.20 (0.12)	2.31	0.13
<i>Day 5 to day 15 (period of experimental manipulation)</i>			
Telomere length day 5	-0.26 (0.09)	4.20	0.04
Sex (Male)	0.07 (0.07)	0.89	0.35
Amount (Plenty)	0.12 (0.06)	3.48	0.06
Effort (Hard)	-0.13 (0.06)	3.84	0.05
Amount*Effort	0.08 (0.13)	0.35	0.55
<i>Day 15 to day 56 (end of experimental manipulation to juvenile period)</i>			
Telomere length day 15	-0.09 (0.06)	2.26	0.13
Sex (Male)	0.03 (0.04)	0.59	0.44
Amount (Plenty)	0.08 (0.05)	2.13	0.14
Effort (Hard)	-0.03 (0.05)	0.33	0.57
Amount*Effort	-0.30 (0.07)	13.12	<0.01

Table S6. Linear mixed model results for oxidative damage to DNA (pg 8-OHdG/ μ g DNA) at days 5, 15 and 56.

Effect	Parameter estimate (s.e.)	LRT	p-value
<i>Day 5</i>			
Sex (Male)	-8.14 (30.90)	0.07	0.79
Amount (Plenty)	12.40 (35.18)	0.84	0.36
Effort (Hard)	41.07 (37.04)	0.01	0.91
Amount*Effort	-66.78 (45.37)	2.06	0.15
<i>Day 15</i>			
Sex (Male)	31.94 (32.81)	0.93	0.33
Amount (Plenty)	76.42 (41.36)	0.77	0.38
Effort (Hard)	58.00 (43.37)	0.03	0.86
Amount*Effort	-89.37 (52.97)	2.72	0.10
<i>Day 56</i>			
Sex (Male)	13.17 (18.72)	0.48	0.49
Amount (Plenty)	43.43 (20.67)	0.45	0.50
Effort (Hard)	84.70 (21.83)	1.70	0.19
Amount*Effort	-101.52 (26.48)	11.40	<0.01

Table S7. Linear mixed model results for plasma inflammation markers high sensitivity C-reactive protein (HS-CRP) and interleukin-6 (IL-6), at age 20 months, with experimental treatments as the predictors.

Effect	Parameter estimate (s.e.)	LRT	p-value
<i>Sqrt(HS-CRP)</i>			
Sex (Male)	0.23 (0.38)	0.37	0.54
Amount (Plenty)	-0.96 (0.46)	0.34	0.56
Effort (Hard)	-1.18 (0.49)	1.01	0.31
Amount*Effort	1.41 (0.60)	5.05	0.02
<i>Log(IL-6)</i>			
Sex (Male)	-1.22 (0.46)	4.52	0.03
Amount (Plenty)	0.55 (0.56)	2.27	0.13
Effort (Hard)	0.21 (0.60)	3.52	0.06
Amount*Effort	-2.40 (0.71)	8.33	<0.01

Table S8. Linear mixed model results for plasma inflammation markers high sensitivity C-reactive protein (HS-CRP) and interleukin-6 (IL-6), at age 20 months, with telomere length change (D from day 5 to day 56) and day 56 8-OHdG as the predictors. To improve homogeneity of residual variance in these models, day 56 8-OHdG was square-root transformed.

Effect	Parameter estimate (s.e.)	LRT	p-value
<i>Sqrt(HS-CRP)</i>			
Sex (Male)	0.85 (0.36)	5.02	0.03
Telomere length change day 5-day 56	-0.48 (0.75)	0.41	0.52
Day 56 8-OHdG (sqrt)	-0.08 (0.05)	1.95	0.16
<i>Log(IL-6)</i>			
Sex (Male)	-0.62 (0.48)	1.64	0.20
Telomere length change day 5-day 56	0.07 (0.96)	<0.01	0.95
Day 56 8-OHdG (sqrt)	0.20 (0.07)	6.95	<0.01

References

1. Verhulst, S., Aviv, A., Benetos, A., Berenson, G. S. & Kark, J. D. Do leukocyte telomere length dynamics depend on baseline telomere length? An analysis that corrects for 'regression to the mean'. *Eur. J. Epidemiol.* **28**, 859–866 (2013).